

Neighbourhood-scale Urban Heat Island Modelling Using ADMS-Urban Climate Model

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Summary

Modelling and mapping urban heat island intensity, as well as predicting its future evolution, can contribute to rational urban planning to address current and future challenges caused by high temperature. This study used ADMS-Urban climate model to simulate near-surface air temperature in Birmingham and the West Midlands, UK. The model outputs include the current spatial distribution of temperatures in Birmingham and the West Midlands, as well as the interannual variability of air temperature on selected receptors. The expected output also includes projected trends in urban heat island intensity under a range of future scenarios.

KEYWORDS: Urban climate modelling, Urban heat island, Air temperature, ADMS-Urban

1. Introduction and background

Urban heat island (UHI) refers to the phenomenon where the air or surface temperature in urban areas is higher than that in surrounding rural areas. The difference in surface thermal properties between urban and rural areas, like heat absorption and storage capacities, evapotranspiration rate, and albedo, are major factors contributing to the UHI (Oke, 2002; Stull, 2012). Other factors contributing to UHI include urban geometry and anthropogenic heat release.

UHI may cause various adverse impacts on the well-being of residents and urban sustainability, like

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health hazard, increasing energy consumption, and air pollution. Therefore, it is necessary to quantify, map, and simulate the intensity, spatial patterns, and future trends of UHI through modelling. Such modelling can facilitate rational urban planning to address the various challenges caused by high temperatures and improve the adaptability of urban areas to climate change. Atmospheric Dispersion Modelling System-Urban Temperature and Humidity (ADMS-Urban T&H) developed by Cambridge Environmental Research Consultants (CERC) offers high temporal and spatial resolution and large spatial coverage, making it suitable for neighbourhood-scale near-surface air temperature modelling in urban and metropolitan areas (Hamilton et al., 2014). ADMS-Urban T&H models local perturbations to the upwind boundary layer profiles, mainly by calculating the ground and latent heat flux associated with surface thermal properties and moisture availability. It also considers the contributions of surface geometry and altitude to temperature (CERC, 2023).

This study applied ADMS-Urban T&H to simulate the spatial distribution and temporal variation of UHI intensity in Birmingham and the West Midlands, UK, to assess the current temperature distribution pattern and to explore potential responses under future scenarios. Birmingham has significant socio-economic inequalities (Pugh and Stubbs, 2023), which makes residents, especially the elderly and the economically disadvantaged group, exhibit a high degree of vulnerability to heat-related health hazards. Currently, Birmingham and the West Midlands, where Birmingham is located, are at a key phase of industrial transformation and urban regeneration, including the extensive implementation of green infrastructure and the restructuring of land cover (Lee et al., 2016). Therefore, quantitatively predicting the urban-scale evolution trend of UHI intensity is crucial for identifying how urban transformation alters residents' heat exposure, thereby enhancing the region's adaptation to climate change and increasingly frequent extreme heat events.

The study is divided into two parts: the first part presents a study simulating air temperature in Birmingham in 2019 and evaluating the model's performance based on the simulation outputs (Zhong et al., 2025). The second part extends the modelling framework by expanding the simulation range to the entire West Midlands region and simulates both the existing scenario (as a baseline) and future scenarios.

2. Modelling urban heat island in Birmingham

This section describes a modelling study aimed at quantifying and mapping the UHI intensity of 2019 in Birmingham. In this study, the model domain was set as a square defined by the long axis of the Birmingham administrative boundary, with an additional 15% outward buffer on all sides. A range of datasets were collected, processed, and used as model inputs, including:

(1) Terrain and urban canopy parameters

The terrain input file (250 m resolution) was extracted from the Ordnance Survey (OS) terrain dataset. Based on a 3-dimensional building layer from OS, an urban canopy file (a gridded dataset with the same resolution and coverage as the terrain data) was created. This urban canopy file contained average building height, λ_p (building coverage at ground level), and average λ_F (building fascias for multiple directions) values for each grid cell. Surface roughness (representing the height of any obstacles present in the model domain) and normalised building volume (NBV, representing building density) input files were derived from these three values in the urban canopy file.

(2) Upwind meteorological input file

Four meteorological stations situated near the domain boundaries - oriented to the north, south, east, and west - were designated as upwind stations. Hourly temperature data for the four stations in the modelling year were obtained from the UK Met Office Weather Observation Website, representing atmospheric conditions before airflow entered the model domain. The model domain was divided into four upwind sectors, with the domain centre as the vertex and the angle bisectors between adjacent upwind stations as boundaries. Based on the sector corresponding to the hourly wind direction (from the Elmdon weather station near the centre of the model domain), temperature data from the relevant upwind station, were compiled into the meteorological input file, together with relative humidity and cloud cover from Elmdon.

(3) Land-use-related parameters

We combined land cover data from UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH) (primarily rural areas), OpenStreetMap vector data (urban and suburban areas), and road network data from OS, to create the land cover map of the model domain. Based on this map, each land cover type was assigned values for three parameters: thermal admittance, surface resistance to evaporation, and albedo, following values reported in previous studies. By calculating area-weighted averages for each grid cell, the land cover map was rasterised into three 50 m resolution layers representing these parameters. Finally, parameter values corresponding to the land use types at the meteorological stations of each sector were assigned to the outer edges of the raster (three-cell width), after which the layers were converted into the corresponding 50 m resolution model input files.

We modelled the UHI intensity of Birmingham for 2019 and evaluated the model output to assess its performance. The output includes (1) long-term (covering the entire year of 2019) near-surface air temperature and perturbation results at 13 receptors within the model domain, and (2) instantaneous spatial distributions (50 m resolution) of air temperature and perturbation during a sunny summer daytime period (11:00 on 26 August 2019) (Figure 1). The two types of outputs were validated using personal weather station (PWS) measurements at the receptor locations and land surface temperature (LST) data retrieved from Landsat 8 satellite imagery at the same time (11:00 on 26 August 2019), respectively. The model's simulation of temporal temperature variations at specific stations and spatial temperature distribution within the model domain align closely with the records from PWS and LST used for evaluation, thereby verifying the reliability of the model. However, for the receptor run outputs, the model tends to underestimate temperatures during the winter, spring, and autumn months, which may be because of the absence of anthropogenic heat sources in the modelling. Comparison between the contour run outputs and LST indicates that the model overestimates temperatures for certain land cover types, particularly grassland, heather, and deciduous woodland, while underestimating temperatures in some residential areas. Therefore, it is necessary to appropriately adjust the thermal property parameters associated with these land use types to better reflect the specific conditions of Birmingham.

Figure 1: The contour model run output for the 26th of August at 11:00 UTC.

3. Model optimizing and expansion

According to the evaluation results of the Birmingham model, the land-use-related input parameters were adjusted to better represent the conditions of Birmingham and West Midlands. The adjustments mainly focus on thermal admittance and surface resistance to evaporation, which are strongly correlated with temperature. Specifically, the surface resistance of residential areas was increased, while that of grass and woodlands was reduced to different degrees. This is to more accurately reflect the moisture of various land cover types in the study area, thereby enabling a more precise estimation of latent heat flux and the resulting cooling effect. Road surface and hard standings' thermal admittance were increased to more accurately characterize the capacity of road surfaces and hard standings to absorb and store daytime solar radiation, which were undervalued in prior simulations. The effectiveness of these adjustments was confirmed through pilot testing within the Birmingham domain.

We are committed to extending the optimized Birmingham model to cover the entire West Midlands, which allows the robustness of the model under broader conditions to be tested. The domain of West Midlands modelling was defined using the same method as the Birmingham model (15% outward expansion of the square of the administrative boundary). The year 2023 was selected as the baseline scenario. New upwind weather stations were identified, and corresponding upwind sectors and meteorological input files were configured. A land cover map for the new domain was generated using methods consistent with the Birmingham model and rasterised into three input files using the adjusted parameters (Figure 2). New terrain file and files related to urban canopy (Figure 3) were also prepared. Similar to the output of Birmingham modelling, short-term spatial temperature distribution maps and temperature temporal variations at receptors (weather stations) will be output for model evaluation. Then, monthly mean temperatures, average daily maximum and minimum temperatures, as well as mean and daily maximum temperatures during heatwave events, which are the critical periods when residents are most susceptible to heat-related health risks, will be simulated.

After the baseline, future scenarios will also be modelled. The UHI conditions under future scenarios

(e.g. the 2050s) will involve the simulation of urbanisation, urban regeneration, and changes in green space. During future scenario modelling, the land cover map and the corresponding three surface attribute input files will be updated based on information provided by planning documents, investment prospectuses, and/or strategic reports from local authorities, to reflect changes in surface properties associated with land-use change. In addition to land cover changes, future scenarios may also include changes in the UHI caused by alterations in anthropogenic heat emission, as well as the effects of future changes in local climate and meteorological conditions.

Figure 2: Three land-use-related model input parameters: **(a)** thermal admittance ($\text{J m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1/2} \text{K}^{-1}$), **(b)** surface resistance to evaporation (s m^{-1}), and **(c)** albedo (-) in the model domain.

Figure 3: (a) Terrain (m) and the two parameters derived from the urban canopy file: (b) surface roughness (m) and (c) NBV in the model domain (m) in the model domain.

4. Output of the modelling

The output of the modelling not only validates the applicability of the ADMS-Urban T&H model on the metropolitan scale, but also directly supports local authorities in developing planning strategies that effectively protect vulnerable populations from heat exposure risks during urban development and regeneration processes.

Specifically, as the 2023 baseline outputs, this study will produce high-resolution spatial mapping of near-surface air temperature across the entire West Midlands. By integrating temperature distributions with demographic data and socio-economic indicators through spatial overlay analysis, the study will identify areas with the highest heat exposure risk (i.e., vulnerability hotspots), as well as the critical periods when vulnerable populations are most at risk. This will provide evidence base for local governments to develop climate adaptation strategies and interventions.

Furthermore, by comparing the baseline model with various scenarios, the study is expected to quantitatively reveal the quantitative impact of external environmental changes in the future (such as urbanisation and climate change) on the intensity and distribution patterns of UHI. Such a comparative

study can assess whether urbanisation and regeneration processes exacerbate heat exposure risks, as well as evaluate the effectiveness of green infrastructure expansion in mitigating these risks.

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Biographies

Yanzhi Lu is a postdoctoral fellow in the Department of Civil Engineering, the University of Birmingham. His research focuses on the intersection of environmental science and urban geography, with a particular interest in urban green infrastructure and urban sustainability. He is currently working on urban climate modelling in West Midlands.

Dr Jenny Stocker is an Associate Director (Research) at Cambridge Environmental Research Consultants (CERC). She has expertise in local climate and air quality modelling and knowledge of the associated physical and chemical processes. Jenny works on model evaluation, aiming to improve models. She is co-author of over 50 papers.

Dr Victoria Hamilton is a Senior Scientist at Cambridge Environmental Research Consultants (CERC). She is experienced in setting up and validating models across the ADMS software suite, including the ADMS-Urban Temperature and Humidity model. Her work focusses on air quality and atmospheric modelling.

Kate Johnson is a Senior Scientist at Cambridge Environmental Research Consultants (CERC). She has expertise in data processing and analysis of large amounts of detailed data, specialising in air quality, geographical and meteorological datasets. Kate's work spans industrial, urban and regional applications.

Jian Zhong is a Senior Lecturer in Urban Environment at the University of Greenwich. He has expertise in urban climate modelling, air quality modelling, Computational Fluid Dynamics and geographical data mapping. His research aims to improve the understanding of urban environmental processes and mechanisms by developing and applying a range of state-of-the-art meteorological and air quality models.